

Current Account Balance Analysis of ASEAN Countries

Chanoknath Sutanapong★

About the author

★Chanoknath Sutanapong is an independent researcher. She may be reached by email at: Chanoknath.sutanapong@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to provide a practical tool for binomial proportion in two sample studies. This binomial proportion of two sample analysis is a special case because it deals with discrete data. A discrete data is a categorical data where the category of interest is designated as 1 else 0. The data used in this paper comes from the IMF's annual report for World Economic Outlook. We extracted the current account balance as a percentage of the GDP as the unit of analysis. The countries of focus are the 10 countries in the ASEAN. The research question is "which country in the ASEAN effectively manage its economy on the basis of current account balance as a percentage of the GDP?" We defined positive current account balance as 1 and negative value as 0. The study period runs from 2005 to 2014. We found that no country in the ASEAN had significant positive current account balance

Keywords: current account, GDP, international trade management, ASEAN

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this paper is to provide a statistical tool to analyze discrete data through the use of two sample proportion. Two samples analysis is a common practice in the industry where one sample may be divided into two portion and both are analyzed. The comparison studies of these two samples may provide a clearer insight into the original sample and, hence, their origin or process from which the original sample came.

The two sample proportion introduced in this paper is used for discrete data. Discrete data are those that may be classified as categorical data. Given a data set that is not quantitative, the researcher identifies a class or category of interest in the set. The data element that meets the criterion is coded with 1 and those that do not meet the criteria are marked with 0. Thus, at the end, we have two categories: (1,0); this is called categorical data.

The basis for categorical data analysis begins with the Laplace definition of the probabilities of success (p) and failure (q). These p and q are defined as: $p = (s + 1) / (n + 2)$ where s is the sum of 1 and the (1,0) codification, and $q = 1 - p$. (Laplace, 1886; de Moivre, 1716[2000]; de la Vallée-

Poussin, 1907; Kenney and Keeping, 1951; Mirimanoff, 1930; Upensky, 1937). The statistical significance test for discrete data is given by the DeMoivre-Laplace Theorem:

$$Z = \frac{S_{x=1} - np}{\sqrt{npq}} \quad (1)$$

where $S_{x=1}$ is the sum of all observation coded as 1, n is the sample size, p and q are defined above (Walker, 1985).

To illustrate this concept, the data of current account balance as a percentage of the GDP of the 10 countries in ASEAN are used. The research question is “which country in ASEAN effectively and efficiently manages its international trade flow?” We defined (i) *effective management of international trade* as positive CA balance as percentage of the GDP and (ii) *efficient international trade management* as statistically significant counts of 1 in the (1,0) categorization in the study period. We examined 10 countries over a period of 5 years spanning from 2010 to 2014.

2.0 DATA

Secondary data of the current account balance as a percentage of the GDP for the ASEAN 10 countries were used for this study. Since the subject matter deals with macro-economic data, only secondary data may be used. Primary data is not practicable.

The sample size of 5 years is based on the recommendation under the Anderson-Darling test that adequate sample size may be achieved at 5 elements. In this paper, we used 5 years of current account as a percentage of the GDP in 10 ASEAN countries from 2010 to 2014. The data was obtained from the IMF’s annual; report of the World Economic Outlook; this data is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. ASEAN countries current account as percentage of the GDP FY2010-2014

Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Brunei	36.60	34.71	29.84	20.88	30.73
Cambodia	(9.29)	(5.89)	(8.19)	(12.98)	(9.82)
Indonesia	0.70	0.19	(2.66)	(3.18)	(3.09)
Laos	(16.49)	(15.27)	(26.04)	(28.40)	(20.03)
Malaysia	10.08	10.89	5.17	3.48	4.39
Myanmar	(1.10)	(1.84)	(4.00)	(4.88)	(2.17)
Philippines	3.60	2.52	2.78	4.19	3.78
Singapore	23.44	22.15	17.00	16.52	18.68
Thailand	3.37	2.54	(0.43)	(1.16)	3.74
Vietnam	(3.79)	0.17	5.96	4.54	4.88

Source: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2018/01/weodata/index.aspx>

The value in Table 1 is categorized into (1,0) by the following definition: positive current account balance as a percentage of the GDP is classified as success and is coded as 1; negative value is coded as 0. This process of discretization of the data is presented Table 2. After coding, the probabilities of success and failure with their attendant significance test are accomplished as defined in equation (1), *supra*.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The objective is to study two sample proportions from two populations and make conclusion about the population. The case involves binomial distribution. There are two populations: populations A and B. In each population there are classes of interest: A and B. A sample is randomly selected from each population. Each sample has a sample size of n_1 and n_2 with a corresponding sample

proportions of p_1 and p_2 respectively. The population proportion are given by π_1 and π_2 . The structure of this comparison study is illustrated by the figure below.

Fig. Population proportion

The objective of the test is to determine whether the assumed equality of population proportion $\pi_1 = \pi_2$ based on two samples: one sample taken from each population. The null hypothesis claims that $\pi_1 = \pi_2$. The test compares the sample proportion and determine whether $p_1 = p_2$. If the samples are significantly different, then it is conclude that the population proportions are also different.

The two samples in this case are the two groups of the ASEAN countries. There are 10 countries in ASEAN. The 10 countries are divided as group 1 which of 6 countries: Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand. Group 2 consists of Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam. The object of the test is to verify whether the two groups are significantly different. Under the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) framework, the ASEAN community should be homogenous, at least in economic terms. Thus, as a test for this policy and vision of “oneness”, we are using the current account balance as a percentage of the GDP as a proxy to test for their homogeneity. We opted for the current account balance as a percentage of the GDP because among the 10 countries, the GDP values are diverse. Singapore, for instance, show the highest level of GDP and Myanmar the lowest. However, this difference unbalanced diversity is controlled when we look at the current account balance as a percentage of the GDP; thus, selection bias is minimized.

3.1 Binomial Distribution

Binomial distribution is defined as random variable X with parameter n and p where X is the cumulative outcome, n is number of trials and p is the number of success. This binomial distribution may be written as $X \approx B(n, p)$ with a *probability mass function* given by:

$$f(k; n, p) = \Pr(X = k) = \binom{n}{k} p^k (1 - p)^{n-k} \quad (2)$$

For $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$ and where $\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ reads “ n choose k .” The n is the number of trials and k is number of success (Papoulis *et al.*, 2002; Feller, 1968). This means k success and $n - k$ failure. The probability of success is p^k . Failure is represented by $n - k$; therefore, the probability

of failure is $(1 - p)^{n-k}$. Recall that binomial distribution occurs in a two category answers: {yes | no} or {success | failure} outcome.

A random experiment involving two possible outcome: success or failure, in a repetitious fashion is called *Bernoulli Trials*. An illustrative example is the tossing of a coin. There are only two outcomes: either the coin would land head or tail. Successive repetition of the tossing would allow us to derive a rule of probability of the two possible outcome if the total number of tossing n and the number of *heads* turning up. Assume that “head” is classified as a “success” and success is symbolized by k . The probability of success may be written as p and the probability of failure (tail) is simply $1 - p$. The distribution of the probability of the outcome is called *binomial distribution*. The preceding description is for Bernoulli distribution because it involves *one kind of Bernoulli trial*, i.e. coin tossing. If the trial involves many kinds of trials, i.e. coin, {yes | no} questions, at the same time, then a new type of binomial distribution is needed to explain the distribution: Poisson distribution (Poisson, 1837; p.206)

A Poisson sampling exists when in a given population, each element of the population is subject to a Bernoulli trial. Each element in the sample may have a different probability of success in the trials. The *probability mass function* for the Poisson distribution is different from that of the Bernoulli type:

$$f(k; \lambda) = P(X = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!} \tag{3}$$

where $k!$ = number of success (k factorial); e = Euler constant or base of the natural logarithm i.e. $e = 2.718...$; and λ = variance of the outcome: $\lambda = E(X) = Var(X)$.

The mean of the Poisson distribution is lambda: λ . The mean deviation is given by (Johnson *et al.*, 1993):

$$E|X - \lambda| = 2 \exp(-\lambda) \frac{\lambda^{\lfloor \lambda \rfloor + 1}}{\lfloor \lambda \rfloor!} \tag{4}$$

The bound for the median (Choi, 1994) is given by:

$$\lambda - \ln 2 \leq v < \lambda + \frac{1}{3} \tag{5}$$

The bound for the tails probability (Massimo *et al.*, 2007) is given by:

$$P(X \geq x) \leq \frac{e^{-\lambda} (e\lambda)^x}{x^x}, \text{ for } x > \lambda \tag{6a}$$

$$P(X \geq x) \leq \frac{e^{-\lambda x^x} (e\lambda)^x}{x^x}, \text{ for } x < \lambda \tag{6b}$$

Therefore, the confidence interval for the Poisson distribution is:

$$\frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^x}{x!} \leq \lambda \leq \frac{e^{-\lambda} (\lambda+1)^x}{x!} \quad (7)$$

The Poisson distribution comes from the *Poisson process*. Poisson process is a stochastic process which (i) counts the number of event, (ii) events occur within a fixed time interval: $\{N(t); t \geq 0\}$. For instance, telephone calls (Willkomm *et al.*, 2009) within a time interval (one hour) in a Customer Service Center. We will leave the subject of Poisson distribution at this introduction to different types of binomial distribution and will revisit the subject in future paper.

3.2 Test Statistic for the Z-test for equality between proportions in binomial distribution

Given two populations with a specified class of interest proportions of π_1 and π_2 . Two random samples are drawn from each population. The proportions in the sample are given by p_1 for sample one corresponding to the population proportion π_1 , and p_2 corresponding to the population proportion π_2 . The test statistic to determine the level of significance of the difference between the population proportions on the basis of sample proportion, i.e. determine the sample proportion and make a conclusion about the population. The test statistic for the equality between two proportions in binomial distribution is given by:

$$Z = \frac{(p_1 - p_2)}{\sqrt{P(1-P) \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}} \quad (8)$$

where $P = \frac{p_1 n_1 + p_2 n_2}{n_1 + n_2}$.

The hypothesis formulated as: $H_0 : \pi_1 = \pi_2$ and $H_A : \pi_1 \neq \pi_2$. Reject the null hypothesis if $\pi_1 \neq \pi_2$. The test may be one-tailed or two-tailed. The Z-critical is given by $Z_{\alpha}(0.05) = \pm 1.96$.

4.0 FINDING AND DISCUSSION

We present the findings in two parts. First, we treated the data under continuous distribution and verify the significance level of the countries that had effective current account balance as a percentage of its GDP. We define effective current account balance as a positive value. Negative account balance comes from excessive imports; we classified such a case as ineffective account balance management. Under this approach to evaluate the country on macro-economic data, the GDP alone is not adequate. By its nature unless the country suffers from economic crisis of shock, the GDP general grows from year to year. However, the current account balance status tells us whether that growth in the GDP stays in the country or does it grow numerically, but at the same time flow out of the country to pay for imports. Thus, despite GDP growth, if the current account balance is negative, the GDP growth is not meaningful.

4.1 Significance test in continuous probability

Under continuous probability analysis, we found that Brunei has a significant CA as percentage of the GDP in the five years period that we studied ($p = 0.02$). As a group, the ASEAN has effective international trade management as measured by CA as percentage of the GDP with exception of one year in 2013 where the number was negative; the average for the five years period (2010 – 2014) is 4.57 ± 2.67 . In 2006, there was a significant improvement in CA for the group ($p = 0.04$).

Table 3. Significance level for current account balance by country and group under continuous probability analysis

Country	Per Country	ASEAN	Z	F(Z)	$p = 1 - F(Z)$
Brunei	35.94*	6.25**	2.00***	0.9782	0.02
Cambodia	(6.90)	9.19	(1.08)	0.1392	0.86
Indonesia	(0.18)	7.49	(0.52)	0.3029	0.70
Laos	(17.51)	3.75	(1.43)	0.0756	0.92
Malaysia	11.00	4.36	0.45	0.6724	0.33
Myanmar	(0.71)	4.71	(0.36)	0.3577	0.64
Philippines	3.50	5.02	(0.10)	0.4593	0.54
Singapore	20.24	1.94	1.23	0.8913	0.11
Thailand	1.92	(0.10)	0.14	0.5540	0.45
Vietnam	(1.60)	3.11	(0.32)	0.3757	0.62

*Country value is the average over a period of 5 years: 2010 – 2014. **ASEAN value is the ASEAN average over a period of 5 years: 2010 – 2014. ***Standard score: $Z = (X_i - \bar{X}) / S$ where X_i is for country's average, \bar{X} is the ASEAN mean and S is the ASEAN standard deviation.

4.2 Significance test in discrete probability

The results under discrete probability analysis are similar to that found under continuous probability method. For individual countries, there is no member country in ASEAN that show significant positive CA as percentage of the GDP ($p > 0.05$). As a group, the average probability for success in having positive CA as percentage of the GDP is 0.53 ± 0.04 .

Table 4. Significance level for current account balance by country and group under discrete probability analysis

Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	pValue
Brunei	1	1	1	1	1	0.68
Cambodia	0	0	0	0	0	0.82
Indonesia	1	1	0	0	0	0.47
Laos	0	0	0	0	0	0.82
Malaysia	1	1	1	1	1	0.68
Myanmar	0	0	0	0	0	0.82
Philippines	1	1	1	1	1	0.68
Singapore	1	1	1	1	1	0.68
Thailand	1	1	0	0	1	0.34
Vietnam	0	1	1	1	1	0.32
p ASEAN	0.58	0.67	0.50	0.50	0.58	
q	0.42	0.33	0.50	0.50	0.42	
Z	0.11	0.22	-	-	0.11	
$F(Z)$	0.54	0.59	0.50	0.50	0.54	
p Value	0.46	0.41	0.50	0.50	0.46	

The pValue is defined as $1 - F(Z)$ and $F(Z)$ is defined as:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{\pi}(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z))} \quad (9)$$

where $Z = (X_i - \bar{X}) / S$, $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The aim of this paper is to answer the question of how to measure effective international trade management? We used the current account balance as percentage of the GDP as the indicator. Ten countries of the ASEAN were used as proxy. We analyze the ASEAN countries as a group and individual countries. The study period span from 2010 to 2014. We classified this significance as *efficient* international trade management, and effective management of international trade is defined as positive CA as percentage of the GDP. No country in ASEAN qualified as *efficient* in international trade management under 95% confidence interval. Among the 10 countries, Thailand and Vietnam scored the highest at 0.6620 and 0.6728 probability of success (effective management of international trade) with pValues of 0.34 and 0.32 respectively which exceeds the allowable significance level of $p < 0.05$. As a group, ASEAN or the AEC (ASEAN Economic Community) has an average of 0.53 level of effectiveness in international trade management ($p = 0.47$).

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